

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 28

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each psalm offers. Each psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 28:1 To You, O LORD, I call; My ^arock, do not be deaf to me, For if You ^bare silent to me, I will become like those who ^cgo down to the pit. ² Hear the ^avoice of my supplications when I cry to You for help, When I ^blift up my hands ^ctoward ¹Your holy ^dsanctuary. ³ ^aDo not drag me away with the wicked And with those who work iniquity, Who ^bspeak peace with their neighbors, While evil is in their hearts. ⁴ Requite them ^aaccording to their work and according to the evil of their practices; Requite them according to the deeds of their hands; Repay them their ¹recompense. ⁵ Because they ^ado not regard the works of the LORD Nor the deeds of His hands, He will tear them down and not build them up.</p>	<p>Psa. 28:1 צוֹרִי אֶל-תַּחַרְשׁ לִמְנִי פֶן-תִּחַשֶׁה מִמְנִי וְנִמְשַׁלְתִּי עִם-יֹרְדֵי בֹרַי : ² שְׁמַע קוֹל תַּחֲנוּנָי בְּשׁוֹעֵי אֱלֹהִים בְּנִשְׁאֵי יָדַי אֶל-דִּבְרֵי קִדְשֶׁךָ : ³ אֶל-תִּמְשַׁכְנֵי עִם-דֹּשְׁעִים וְעִם- פְּעֵלֵי אֲוֶן דִּבְרֵי שְׁלוֹם עִם-רַעֲיֵיהֶם וְרַעְיָה בְּלִבָּבָם : ⁴ תֵּן-לָהֶם כְּפַעֲלָם וּכְרַע מַעַלְלֵיהֶם כְּמַעֲשֵׂה יְדֵיהֶם תֵּן לָהֶם הַשֵּׁב וּגְמוּלָם לָהֶם : ⁵ כִּי לֹא יִבְיִנוּ אֶל-פְּעֻלֹת יְהוָה וְאֶל- מַעֲשֵׂה יָדָיו יִתְרַסֹּם וְלֹא יִבְנֶם : ⁶ בָּרוּךְ יְהוָה כִּי-שָׁמַע קוֹל תַּחֲנוּנָי : ⁷ יְהוָה אֱעִי וּמִגְנִי בֹו בָטַח לִבִּי וְנִעַנְרַתִּי וַיַּעֲלֵז לִבִּי וּמְשִׁירִי אַהֲדִנּוּ : ⁸ יְהוָה עֲזֹ-לִמּוֹ וּמְעֹז יְשׁוּעוֹת מְשִׁיחוֹ הוּא : ⁹ הוֹשִׁיעָה אֶת- עַמּוֹךָ וּבָרֵךְ אֶת-נַחֲלֹתֶךָ וְרַעַם וְנִשְׂאֵם עַד-הָעוֹלָם :</p>
<p>Psa. 28:6 Blessed be the LORD, Because He ^ahas heard the voice of my supplication. ⁷ The LORD is my ^astrength and my ^bshield; My heart ^ctrusts in Him, and I am helped; Therefore ^dmy heart exults, And with ^emy song I shall thank Him.</p>	

<p>⁸ The LORD is ¹their ^astrength, And He is a ^{2b}saving defense to His anointed.</p> <p>⁹ ^aSave Your people and bless ^bYour inheritance; Be their ^cshepherd also, and ^dcarry them forever.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 28:1 ^aPs 18:2 ^bPs 35:22; 39:12; 83:1 ^cPs 88:4; 143:7; Prov 1:12</p> <p>Psalm 28:2 ¹Lit <i>the innermost place of Your sanctuary</i> ^aPs 140:6 ^bPs 134:2; 141:2; Lam 2:19; 1 Tim 2:8 ^cPs 5:7; 138:2 ^d1 Kin 6:5</p> <p>Psalm 28:3 ^aPs 26:9 ^bPs 12:2; 55:21; 62:4; Jer 9:8</p> <p>Psalm 28:4 ¹Or <i>dealings</i> ^aPs 62:12; 2 Tim 4:14; Rev 18:6; 22:12</p> <p>Psalm 28:5 ^aIs 5:12</p> <p>Psalm 28:6 ^aPs 28:2</p> <p>Psalm 28:7 ^aPs 18:2; 59:17 ^bPs 3:3 ^cPs 13:5; 112:7 ^dPs 16:9 ^ePs 40:3; 69:30</p>	<p>Psalm 28:8 ¹A few mss and ancient versions read <i>the strength of His people</i> ²Or <i>refuge of salvation</i> ^aPs 20:6; 89:17 ^bPs 27:1; 140:7</p> <p>Psalm 28:9 ^aPs 106:47 ^bDeut 9:29; 32:9; 1 Kin 8:51; Ps 33:12; 106:40 ^cPs 80:1 ^dDeut 1:31; Is 40:11; 46:3; 63:9</p>
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Targum

Psa. 28:1 Of David. To you, O LORD, I cry; O my strength, do not be silent to me, lest, when you are silent, I become like those who descend to the pit. ² Accept the voice of my petition when I pray to you, whenever I spread my hands in prayer before your temple. ³ Do not drag me away with the wicked or with those who do wrong; who speak peace with their fellows, while evil is in their hearts. ⁴ Give to them according to their deeds, and according to their evil deeds; according to the works of their hands, repay them; turn upon them their retribution. ⁵ Because they do not understand the Torah of the LORD or the works of his hands; he will tear them down and not rebuild them. ⁶ Blessed is the LORD because he has accepted the voice of my prayer. ⁷ The LORD is my strength and shield; on him my heart has set its hope; and you have aided me, and my heart exults; I will give thanks in his presence by my psalm. ⁸ The LORD is their strength and might; he is the redemption of his anointed. ⁹ Redeem your people and bless your inheritance; feed them and support them forever.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This psalm is similar to Psalm 27. In this Psalm, King David asked the LORD to release him from his temporal responsibilities so that he could devote himself to the LORD's service. This action would also allow him to repent for his past sins and bring him closer to the LORD.

Verse one

The LORD being silent, thus not communicating with David, means that the LORD remained distant from him. David desired to get closer and closer to the LORD. Even though he offered prayers, the LORD was not answering him. The souls that go down to the pit are in Sheol, where they are entirely cut off from any communication from the LORD.

To You, O LORD, do I call; My rock is not distant from me, for your silence makes me think you are not concerned with me. It is as if I died and you placed me in Sheol.

Verse two

David expected the LORD to help him because David had given his full devotion to the LORD's Law at this stage of his life.

Hear my supplications when I turn to You for help, when I lift up my hands toward your holy sanctuary.

Verse three

David said that he wants to seek out a future that only follows the path of the Law of the LORD.

Take me away from the lawless and the workers of violence, they speak peace with their neighbors, but evil is in their hearts.

Verse four

פָּעַל (paal) – means “to do.” This word denotes attaining mastery over materials or circumstances as to be able to shape them following one's intentions. Therefore if one's intentions are evil, then their actions will be evil.

Give them according to their deed and according to the evil of their deeds; give them according to the work of their hands, let them be in their deserts, thus cut off from Your love and grace.

Verse five

Evil people have no respect for the LORD. Their actions are that of Satanic influence.

They give no heed to your works, nor the deeds of the LORD's hands; the LORD will tear them down and not build them up.

Verse six & seven

David felt that his prayers had already been heard because he understood the attitudes held by his foes toward the LORD and the Torah. These attitudes are quite different from those which he has always cherished.

Blessed be the LORD, for He has already heard the voice of my supplications.

The LORD is my strength and shield; my heart has trusted in Him, and I received His help; I rejoice and sing songs of praise to Him.

Verse eight

David knew that the LORD was an invincible force, and His power gave salvation to him.

The LORD is an invincible power to them and offers salvation to His anointed.

Verse nine

David knew that the LORD must be trusted. He prayed that His people would come to know Him as their leader (shepherd) forever.

Grant salvation to your people, who are your inheritance, and be their spiritual leader forever.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To You, O LORD, do I call; My rock is not distant from me, for your silence makes me think you are not concerned with me. It is as if I died and you placed me in Sheol.

Hear my supplications when I turn to You for help, when I lift up my hands toward your holy sanctuary.

Take me away from the lawless and the workers of violence, they speak peace with their neighbors, but evil is in their hearts.

Give them according to their deed and according to the evil of their deeds; give them according to the work of their hands, let them be in their deserts, thus cut off from Your love and grace.

They give no heed to your works, nor the deeds of the LORD's hands; the LORD will tear them down and not build them up.

Blessed be the LORD, for He has already heard the voice of my supplications.

The LORD is my strength and shield; my heart has trusted in Him, and I received His help; I rejoice and sing songs of praise to Him.

The LORD is an invincible power to them and offers salvation to His anointed.

Grant salvation to your people, who are your inheritance, and be their spiritual leader forever.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

